

CASRAI, euroCRIS, Lattes, and VIVO: Four Perspectives on Research Information Standards

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August 24, 2012

Format

- A round of quick introductions from the panelists
- Seed questions from the moderator
- Open discussion

Seed questions for introductions

- Where and how did each standard emerge
- Traction gained and current major activities
- Evolution and lessons learned
- Open issues to address

Seed questions for discussion

- What opportunities are there to work together?
- How would this be most productive?
- What other movements/standards are relevant to the research information space?
- What will the research information landscape look like in 5 years, and how can we shape that?

CASRAI: origin, structure, and goals

- Founded in 2006 in response to call from NatSci and SocSci government funding agencies
- Multi-national multi-discipline collaboration on a common modular dictionary for our separate systems
- Not a competing system but a common semantic and structural currency between systems
- A layer of connection between any systems within or across orgs or nations
- Aims to encompass key pillars of academic, government and industry R&D

CASRAI: current major activities

- Expanding to add new national chapters and editions of the common dictionary - UK, US
- Mapping of CERIF and CASRAI
- Collaboration with VIVO on a ontology view of the dictionary
- Adding key international vendors
- Developing data flow pilots with vendors, universities and funders

CASRAI: evolution and lessons learned

- Want to support multiple ‘envelopes’ to carry a common semantic payload - XML, RDF, JSON
- Need a technology-neutral language of modelling comprehensible to business users
- No one chapter can unduly influence or slow another - local first development of elements
- Summer a lousy time for review cycles :)

CASRAI: open issues

- How best to incorporate existing ontologies - do not want to reinvent wheels
- How to swap in or out ontologies by nation or discipline
- National differences in leadership patterns. Funders in one country, universities in another, both in most.
- When the best time to bring in government R&D and industry R&D

euroCRIS: origin, structure, and goals

- 1984 Heads of Research for UK, FR, IT decided on a project for interoperation of research information
 - Demonstrated UK, FR, IT 1987 (IDEAS)
 - Demonstrated G7 1999 (EXIRPTS)
 - In each case homogeneous query over heterogeneous databases
- 1987 EU set up expert group to define standards to allow machine interoperation – **has been the objective ever since**
- 1991 euroCRIS community inaugurated. Researchers, research managers, librarians, innovators, evaluators (scientificometrics), media
 - Conference series
 - Seminar series
 - Strategic partners
 - Task Groups
- 1991, 2000 CERIF (**Common European Research Information Format**) is an EU Recommendation to member States
- 2002 EU requested euroCRIS to maintain, develop, promote CERIF

Long history!

euroCRIS: current major activities

- euroCRIS members in 42 countries on all continents except Antarctica
- CERIF national standard in 9 countries and used (in some form) in research funding, research performing and research utilising institutions in just about all 42
- CERIF used for interoperation:
 - Evaluation by funders of research output, outcomes and impact
 - Benchmarking and comparison
 - Finding collaborators, evaluators (referees, reviewers)
 - Management information and decision support (including statistics, visualisation)
 - Bibliometrics / scientometrics
 - Directories
 - Driving websites
 - Driving LOD/semantic web and interoperating with LOD/semantic web
 - Interoperation with ontologies (OWL, SKOS)
 - B2B between funders and research institutions

Used widely: by region and purpose

euroCRIS: evolution & lessons learned

- **TECHNICAL**

- Originally for file exchange
- Then for homogeneous query over heterogeneous sources
- Then for full interoperability

- **BUSINESS**

- Originally to find out what research is done where by whom
- Expanded to cover outputs (outcomes, impact)
- And funding
- And facilities, services, equipment....

Development steered by community

euroCRIS: open issues

- Interoperation
 - Formal syntax
 - For efficient and effective computer processing
 - Declared semantics
 - For shared understanding by computers and humans
 - Shared dictionaries/ lexicons / thesauri / domain ontologies
- Best Practice
 - Shared experience
 - Convergence of methods
 - ‘Workbench’ for each kind of user
 - Workflowed processes
 - Within working environment – integrated with office / business / research functions

Lattes: origin, structure, and goals

S&T Contents in the curriculum

- *Identification*
- *Addresses*
- *Academic Degrees*
- *Professional Experiences*
- *Knowledge domain*
- *Idioms*
- *Prizes*
- *Projects*
- *Bibliographic Production*
- *Technical Production*
- *Thesis Advisements*
- *Complementary Data*

In 1999 the Brazilian researchers received not an electronic form but an integrated information system that helped them to organize and divulgate their work.

Information Resources

- *Homepage automatic*
- *CV Indicators*
- *Export to several formats*
- *Easy error verification*

Co-production: was very important to involve the Brazilian researchers: CNPq sent questionnaires to more than **700 researchers. About 400 answered telling what they wanted in a CV. About a 100 tested the first version of CV Lattes** and evaluated it as 4.2 (on a 0 to 5 scale)

Lattes: origin, structure, and goals (2)

The data architecture was created to manage **research groups** and **curricula** information.

Different ST&I players views (and services) were considered during the design phase.

The left and right walls represent different criteria to analyze the data (e.g., by knowledge fields or geographic area)

Lattes: evolution and lessons learned

- CNPq just released a renewed Web interface for Lattes.
- Also new features include the ability to **record innovation related activities** such as projects that were developed in partnership with businesses and government agencies, scientific data ingestion and patent records.
- Lesson 1- Project like Lattes should always be in a networked perspective
- Lesson 2 – Plan for change (flexibility is one key aspect) – as an example - Institution Structure will shift,

Lattes: evolution

- Review the architectural standards (almost 14 years old)

- Open Data requirements (Open Government Partnership and new Brazilian regulation)

Lattes: evolution

- Build a Network Ontology perspective like VIVO, eagle-I and bring new perspectives (Research Object Structure, myExperiment, MethodBox)

Wf4Ever ROBox
Connecting Research Objects in your [Dropbox](#) folder

Successfully logged in. Welcome back Wf4Ever Test User

Manage your Research Objects (ROs)

The Wf4Ever ROBox app connects up your Dropbox and synchronises your Research Objects (ROs) with [dLibra](#)

Getting Started

- ✓ 1. Sign in or connect with your Dropbox account
- ✓ 2. Specify a location in your Dropbox to find/store ROs
- ✗ 3. Add some ROs (as folders) with content into this location [Help](#)
- ✗ 4. Wait for the app to sync [Status](#)

✗ Ready! View your Research Objects

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Icons by [Axisis Team](#) and [famfamfam](#)

Lattes: open issues

- Still needs to build a network of researchers
- Discussion on the use of Semantic technology for integration (possibilities of a Lattes Ontology)
- Not yet ready to do Linked Open Data (LOD) or Linked Government Data (LGD)

VIVO and Lattes

← → ↻ www.stela.org.br/semanticsearch/#result&q=%7B%22query%22:%22takeoff%22%7D

 isdc-x
Busca Semântica Integrada

takeoff

82 DOCUMENTOS RECUPERADOS

Tecnical Reports

- AC 135-42 Extended Operations (ETOPS) and Operations in the North Polar Routes.pdf
[Link não disponível](#)
airplane equipment and systems are installed and functioning before **takeoff**, more thorough **flight** (...) crewmember to cope with an adverse **operating** condition. **System** failures or malfunctions occurring
- AC 150-5220-22A Engineered Materials Arresting Systems for Aircraft Overruns.pdf
[Link não disponível](#)
takeoff or while **landing**. Data on aircraft overruns over a 12- year period (1975 to 1987) indicate (...), but **landing** gear configuration and tire pressure. In general, use the **maximum** take-off weight
- AC 23-8B Flight Test Guide Certification Part 23 Airplanes.pdf
[Link não disponível](#)
Navigation **System** AC 23-7 Substantiation for an Increase in **Maximum Weight**, **Maximum Landing Weight** (...) 23.61 TAKEOFF FLIGHT PATH..... 41 25. SECTION
- AC 23-8C Flight Test Guide for Certification of Part 23 Aircraft_DRAFT.pdf
[Link não disponível](#)
23.61 TAKEOFF FLIGHT PATH (...) 73 23.149 MINIMUM CONTROL SPEED
- AC 25-15 Approval of Flight Management Systems in Transport Category Airplanes.pdf
[Link não disponível](#)
speed. 5 25.904 Automatic **takeoff** thrust **control** system (ATTCS). 5 25.1301 Function and installation (...) - engine-inoperative. 5 25.123 En route **flight** paths. 5 25.125 **Landing**. 5 25.149 Minimum **control**
- AC 25-25 Performance and Handling Characteristics in the Icing Conditions Specified in Part 25 Appendix C.pdf
[Link não disponível](#)
. Operative Ice Protection **System** A1-1 a. All **Flight Phases** Except **Takeoff** A1-1 b. **Takeoff** Phase A1 (...) stall and maneuverability evaluations with the airplane under **flight** guidance **system** **control**
- AC 25-7 Chapter 2 Section 2.pdf
[Link não disponível](#)

Ontologia

- Performance
 - Aircraft
 - Aircraft_Component
 - Flight_Controls (7)
 - Wing (1)
 - Development_Stages
 - Common_Definition (4)
 - First_Definition (3)
 - Phase_Out (1)
 - Flight_Data (9)
 - Flight_Manual (13)
 - Performance_Manual (20)
 - Flight_Planning (2)
 - Flight_Stage
 - NonRegulated_Flight_Stage
 - Climb (2)
 - Regulated_Flight_Stage (6)
 - Landing (10)
 - TakeOff (11)
 - Overall_Procedure
 - Operational_Performance (27)
 - Parameter
 - Regulated_Parameter
 - Speed (13)

VIVO: origin, structure, and goals

- Began at Cornell in 2003 for life sciences
- Expanded to whole university 2007-2009
- NIH-funded “VIVO: Enabling National Networking of Scientists” project 2009-2012
- Becoming DuraSpace incubator project for sustainability and independent legal status
- Ontology, tools, and apps in addition to core code
- Advocacy for open data and interoperable data: local, regional, national, & international

VIVO: current major activities

- Transitioning from grant funding to a sustainable community with activities on many fronts
 - Business model projects a blend of smaller grants, in-kind contributions to development and other tasks, corporate and institutional sponsorships, registry of service providers, and direct service offerings
- Projects extending our reach
 - CTSAconnect – research resources & clinical expertise
 - Datastar – research datasets
 - Linked Data for Libraries – scholarly resource discovery
 - AgriVIVO – international agricultural experts & pubs

VIVO: evolution and lessons learned

- In 2007 moved from relational model to semantic web
 - Generalization – application configured by the ontology
 - Leverage many additional tools
 - Ontology and data standards (now called linked open data)
- Nothing is easy
 - Building and updating an enterprise-scale application is always going to be challenging
- Facilitate and enable the community

VIVO: open issues

- Sustainability, at home and collectively
- Relationship to SciENCv and other national-level initiatives (policy & technical issues)
- Definitive references to shared data
 - Moving beyond identifiers to stable, discoverable URIs
- Achieving the interoperability that is technically possible
- Uis and hooks for workable graph-based provenance
- Looking and contributing beyond our own comfort zone (we are not just profiling)

Seed questions for discussion

- What opportunities are there to work together?
- How would this be most productive?
- What other movements/standards are relevant to the research information space?
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Opportunities to work together (KJ)

- The aim has to be machine to machine interoperability
 - at syntactic and semantic levels
 - with local interface for query / update and response / report
- Start with a common syntax for interoperation
 - Query
 - Response
- Then common semantics
 - common vocabulary in a domain ontology
- Then common services (in the sense of web services)
 - Atomic functional processes that can be (re-) composed dynamically
- Then localisation of interfaces
 - Including mobile and various modes

What other standards are relevant? (KJ)

- Identifiers: CERIF allows multiple identifiers and relationships (roles) thus the *purpose* of each ID and its relationship to others can be declared; CERIF recommends UUIDs (standard);
- Generally we can learn much from other standards organisations such as W3C, the library community, the research object metadata community, the digital preservation community and many more

Looking ahead 5 years (KJ)

- Very high expectations from politicians, funders
 - Engine for wealth creation
 - And improved quality of life
- General acceptance of benefits by researchers
 - **Carrots** (publicity) and **sticks** (evaluation)
- Agreed interoperation architecture between CRIS
- Agreed interoperation architecture between the models of the virtualised CRIS
 - User model, data model, processing model, resource model
 - → slide from presentation at CRIS2012 conference

The Plan: Architecture (KJ)

Questions and Discussion

Thank you